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THE IMPORTANCE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON OUR LIFE AND STUDY, HOW IT CAN IMPACT IN EDUCATION

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Abstract: this is paper will discuss the history of ai, the importance of ai (artificial intelligence), how it impacts on our life, learning, and study. This paper also gives us information about advantages and disadvantages and the spread of ai and its role in shaping the future of education.

Key words: importance of ai, how it impact on our life and learning, the history of ai, benefits of and drawbacks of ai.

Introduction. Today's technology has become an unavoidable part of the passage of the time. Technology has not only changed people's lifestyles but has also changed how we work, learn and interact. Various kinds of innovations appear all the time making our activities and work more practical and effective. A more recent technological development is the emergence of the term artificial intelligence (ai) which is currently starting to steal attention as a tool to act like humans. In its development ai has also penetrated the world of education ai systems allow people to learn with the help of education assistants such as bots.

The development to improve the quality of education especially the adjustment of information and communication technology. AI facilitates rapid and efficient dissemination of knowledge.

AI is a study of how human brain think, learn, decide and work when it tries to solve the problem. The aim of ai is to improve computer functions which are connected to human knowledge such as reasoning, learning, problem-solving, belief and linguistic intelligence.

Methods. AI refers to the science and engineering used to make smart systems in computer science domain which helping in technological advancements. AI discovered because of the historic philosophy, imaginations and demonstrations by some of the leading scientific, researchers of old times. Early inventions were

related to the fields like electronics, engineering and many more had severe impact on AI. Artificial intelligence was first reported in 1950s. If AI is not programmed properly it may fail and act contrary to its intended purpose. AI can make organisations more reliant on technology.

AI systems were able to analyse complex algorithms and self-learning, now AI could be applied in clinical practice through risk assessment models, improving diagnostic accuracy and workflow efficiency. DL (deep learning) was an important advancement in artificial intelligence. Deep learning can be trained to classify data on its own. Artificial intelligence provides every learner their own personalized learning experience, teachers are provided with their own AI teaching assistant, consistent support for collaborative learning. AI technologies which are currently in use include converting traffic sensors into intelligent that can automatically detect accidents and useful in prediction of traffic conditions. AI can solve stressful and complex problems that humans may not be able to do. AI can complete assigned tasks much faster than a human being AI make decisions based on data rather than emotion. Within AI itself it is easier to spread knowledge.

Accordingly, these are benefits:

- * helping individual at learning at their own speed
- * practical solution to chronic problems
- * no more paperwork in school
- * prevention of waste of time
- * more effective individual learning process

Artificial intelligence can replace human jobs. If AI is not programmed properly then it can malfunction and do opposite to what it is supposed to do. Due to AI unemployment problems are increase. AI can increase the technological dependency of any organization. Artificial intelligence lacks creativity in responses, manufacturing can result in failure of AI and lead to various problems.

Machines are not able to develop a bond with humans which is a critical part of team management. AI is becoming a major reason for loss of jobs in various industries, lacks human touch and emotional intelligence when we consider its application in field of medicine. here are drawbacks:

- *mechanical thinking of individuals
- *the humanistic values could be replaced by a pragmatic perspective
- *no need for human intervention in education
- *the possibility of uncontrolled intelligence technologies in education
- *negative effects on social media

Discussion. AI has got two sides. AI helps us much more than we thought. For example, study, healthcare and so on. Most of the participants believe that AI will

open up new opportunities for students and learners which normal classroom or educational tools may not deliver. But, there could be problems. Schools must take an active role in preparing for the next industrial revolution.

Conclusion. In my opinion, artificial intelligence is getting everywhere. Its application could be seen in healthcare industry, manufacturing and production, fashion technology, education, security and surveillance, etc. It has become the most trending topic of discussion when we talk about computers in general. AI assistance improved radiologists' performance in distinguishing coronavirus disease 2019 pneumonia from non-coronavirus disease 2019 pneumonia at chest CT (computed tomography). Nowadays, even video games are using AI, which serves to improve game-player experience rather than machine learning or decision making. AI has a bright future ahead.

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